

On Solé and Planat criterion for the Riemann hypothesis

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Abstract

The Riemann hypothesis is a conjecture that the Riemann zeta function has its zeros only at the negative even integers and complex numbers with real part $\frac{1}{2}$. This is one of the Clay Mathematics Institute's Millennium Prize Problems. There are several statements equivalent to the famous Riemann hypothesis. In 2011, Solé and Planat stated that the Riemann hypothesis is true if and only if the inequality $\zeta(2) \cdot \prod_{p \leq p_k} (1 + \frac{1}{p}) > e^\gamma \cdot \log \theta(p_k)$ holds for all prime numbers $p_k > 3$, where $\theta(x)$ is the Chebyshev function, $\gamma \approx 0.57721$ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant, $\zeta(x)$ is the Riemann zeta function and \log is the natural logarithm. Let $\sigma(n)$ denote the sum-of-divisors function of n . We also require the properties of superabundant numbers, that is to say left to right maxima of $n \mapsto \frac{\sigma(n)}{n}$. In this note, using Solé and Planat criterion on superabundant numbers, we prove that the Riemann hypothesis is true.

Keywords: Riemann hypothesis, Superabundant numbers, Sum-of-divisors function, Prime numbers

MSC Classification: 11M26 , 11A41 , 11A25

1 Introduction

The Riemann hypothesis is considered by many to be the most important unsolved problem in pure mathematics. It was proposed by Bernhard Riemann (1859). The Riemann hypothesis belongs to the Hilbert's eighth problem on David Hilbert's list of twenty-three unsolved problems. As usual $\sigma(n)$ is the

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sum-of-divisors function of n

$$\sum_{d|n} d,$$

where $d \mid n$ means the integer d divides n . For each natural number $n > 1$, we give its Abundancy Index as $I(n) = \frac{\sigma(n)}{n}$. Superabundant numbers were defined by Leonidas Alaoglu and Paul Erdős (1944). Let $p_1 = 2, p_2 = 3, \dots, p_k$ denote the first k consecutive primes, then an integer of the form $\prod_{i=1}^k p_i^{a_i}$ with $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k \geq 1$ is called a Hardy-Ramanujan integer [1, pp. 367]. A natural number n is called superabundant precisely when, for all natural numbers $m < n$

$$I(m) < I(n).$$

In mathematics, $\Psi(n) = n \cdot \prod_{p|n} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)$ is called the Dedekind Ψ function. Define, for $n \geq 3$, the ratio $R(n) = \frac{\Psi(n)}{n \cdot \log \log n}$, where \log is the natural logarithm. We say that $\text{Dedekind}(p_k)$ holds provided that

$$R(N_k) > \frac{e^\gamma}{\zeta(2)}$$

where $\gamma \approx 0.57721$ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant, $\zeta(2) = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$ is a famous value of the Riemann zeta function, p_k is the k th prime number and $N_k = \prod_{i=1}^k p_i$ is the primorial number of order k . Next, we have Solé and Planat Theorem:

Proposition 1 *Dedekind(p_k) holds for all prime numbers $p_k > 3$ if and only if the Riemann hypothesis is true [2, Theorem 4.2 pp. 5].*

Putting all together yields the proof of the Riemann hypothesis.

2 What if the Riemann hypothesis were false?

In mathematics, the Chebyshev function $\theta(x)$ is given by

$$\theta(x) = \sum_{p \leq x} \log p$$

with the sum extending over all prime numbers p that are less than or equal to x . We deduce that $\theta(p_k) = \log N_k$, where p_k is the k th prime number and $N_k = \prod_{i=1}^k p_i$ is the primorial number of order k . Several analogues of the Riemann hypothesis have already been proved. Many authors expect (or at least hope) that it is true. However, there are some implications in case of the Riemann hypothesis might be false.

Lemma 2 *If the Riemann hypothesis is false, then there are infinitely many prime numbers p_k for which $\text{Dedekind}(p_k)$ fails (i.e. $\text{Dedekind}(p_k)$ does not hold).*

Proof The Riemann hypothesis is false, if there exists some natural number $x_0 \geq 5$ such that $g(x_0) > 1$ or equivalent $\log g(x_0) > 0$:

$$g(x) = \frac{e^\gamma}{\zeta(2)} \cdot \log \theta(x) \cdot \prod_{p \leq x} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)^{-1}.$$

We know the bound [2, Theorem 4.2 pp. 5]:

$$\log g(x) \geq \log f(x) - \frac{2}{x}$$

where f was introduced in the Nicolas paper [3, Theorem 3 pp. 376]:

$$f(x) = e^\gamma \cdot \log \theta(x) \cdot \prod_{p \leq x} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p}\right).$$

When the Riemann hypothesis is false, then there exists a real number $b < \frac{1}{2}$ for which there are infinitely many natural numbers x such that $\log f(x) = \Omega_+(x^{-b})$ [3, Theorem 3 (c) pp. 376]. According to the Hardy and Littlewood definition, this would mean that

$$\exists k > 0, \forall y_0 \in \mathbb{N}, \exists y \in \mathbb{N} (y > y_0) : \log f(y) \geq k \cdot y^{-b}.$$

That inequality is equivalent to $\log f(y) \geq \left(k \cdot y^{-b} \cdot \sqrt{y}\right) \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{y}}$, but we note that

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow \infty} \left(k \cdot y^{-b} \cdot \sqrt{y}\right) = \infty$$

for every possible positive value of k when $b < \frac{1}{2}$. In this way, this implies that

$$\forall y_0 \in \mathbb{N}, \exists y \in \mathbb{N} (y > y_0) : \log f(y) \geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{y}}.$$

Hence, if the Riemann hypothesis is false, then there are infinitely many natural numbers x such that $\log f(x) \geq \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}}$. Since $\frac{2}{x} = o\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{x}}\right)$, then it would be infinitely many natural numbers x_0 such that $\log g(x_0) > 0$. In addition, if $\log g(x_0) > 0$ for some natural number $x_0 \geq 5$, then $\log g(x_0) = \log g(p_k)$ where p_k is the greatest prime number such that $p_k \leq x_0$. Actually,

$$\prod_{p \leq x_0} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)^{-1} = \prod_{p \leq p_k} \left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)^{-1}$$

and

$$\theta(x_0) = \theta(p_k)$$

according to the definition of the Chebyshev function. □

3 Lower bound on superabundant numbers

We know the following property for the superabundant numbers:

Proposition 3 *If n is superabundant, then n is a Hardy-Ramanujan integer [4, Theorem 1 pp. 450].*

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Lemma 4 *Let $n = \prod_{i=1}^k p_i^{a_i}$ be a superabundant number such that $7^{100} \mid n$. Then*

$$\left(\prod_{i=1}^k \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^{a_i+1}} \right) \cdot \frac{p_i^2}{p_i^2 - 1} \right) > 1.595.$$

Proof Let $\prod_{i=1}^k p_i^{a_i}$ be the representation of this superabundant number n as the product of the first k consecutive primes $p_1 < \dots < p_k$ with the natural numbers $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k \geq 1$ as exponents, since n must be a Hardy-Ramanujan integer by Proposition 3. Due to

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^{a_i+1}} \right) \cdot \frac{p_i^2}{p_i^2 - 1} \geq 1$$

for every prime p_i and whole exponent $a_i \geq 1$, then

$$\left(\prod_{i=1}^k \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^{a_i+1}} \right) \cdot \frac{p_i^2}{p_i^2 - 1} \right) \geq \beta$$

where

$$\beta = \left(\prod_{i=1}^4 \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^{a_i+1}} \right) \cdot \frac{p_i^2}{p_i^2 - 1} \right).$$

In conclusion, we verify that

$$\beta \geq \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{101}} \right) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{3^{101}} \right) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{5^{101}} \right) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{7^{101}} \right) \cdot \frac{4}{3} \cdot \frac{9}{8} \cdot \frac{25}{24} \cdot \frac{49}{48} > 1.595$$

since $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq a_3 \geq a_4 \geq 100$. □

4 Upper bound on superabundant numbers

We use the following inequality and equivalences:

Proposition 5 [5, logarithm pp. 1]. *For $x > -1$:*

$$\log(1 + x) \leq x$$

Proposition 6 [4, Theorem 7 pp. 454]. *Let n be a superabundant number such that p is the largest prime factor of n , then*

$$p \sim \log n, \quad (n \rightarrow \infty).$$

Proposition 7 [6, pp. 1]. *We have*

$$x \sim \theta(x), \quad (x \rightarrow \infty).$$

Lemma 8 *Let n be a large enough superabundant number such that p_k is the largest prime factor of n and the k th prime number. Then*

$$\frac{e^\gamma}{\zeta(2)} \cdot \frac{1.595}{1.56} > \frac{\log \log n}{\log \log N_k}.$$

Proof We know that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\log \log n}{\log \log N_k} &= \frac{\log \log \left(\frac{n}{N_k} \cdot N_k \right)}{\log \log N_k} \\
 &= \frac{\log \left(\log \left(\frac{n}{N_k} \right) + \log N_k \right)}{\log \log N_k} \\
 &= \frac{\log \left(\log N_k \cdot \left(1 + \frac{\log \left(\frac{n}{N_k} \right)}{\log N_k} \right) \right)}{\log \log N_k} \\
 &= \frac{\log \log N_k + \log \left(1 + \frac{\log \left(\frac{n}{N_k} \right)}{\log N_k} \right)}{\log \log N_k} \\
 &= 1 + \frac{\log \left(1 + \frac{\log \left(\frac{n}{N_k} \right)}{\log N_k} \right)}{\log \log N_k} \\
 &\leq 1 + \frac{\log \left(\frac{n}{N_k} \right)}{(\log N_k) \cdot \log \log N_k} \\
 &= 1 + \frac{\log(n) - \log(N_k)}{(\log N_k) \cdot \log \log N_k}
 \end{aligned}$$

by Proposition 5. We only need to prove that

$$\frac{e^\gamma}{\zeta(2)} \cdot \frac{1.595}{1.56} - 1 > \frac{\log(n) - \log(N_k)}{(\log N_k) \cdot \log \log N_k}$$

where $\frac{e^\gamma}{\zeta(2)} \cdot \frac{1.595}{1.56} - 1 > 0$. Let's distribute the inequality to obtain that

$$1 + \left(\frac{e^\gamma}{\zeta(2)} \cdot \frac{1.595}{1.56} - 1 \right) \cdot \log \log N_k > \frac{\log n}{\log N_k}.$$

Since n is a superabundant number, then

$$p_k \sim \log n, \quad (n \rightarrow \infty)$$

by Proposition 6. Moreover,

$$p_k \sim \theta(p_k), \quad (k \rightarrow \infty)$$

by Proposition 7, where $\theta(p_k) = \log N_k$. Consequently, we can assure that the expression

$$\frac{\log n}{\log N_k}$$

deeply decreases while the other

$$1 + \left(\frac{e^\gamma}{\zeta(2)} \cdot \frac{1.595}{1.56} - 1 \right) \cdot \log \log N_k$$

full increases as long as n goes to infinity. Finally, there must exist some m such that

$$\frac{e^\gamma}{\zeta(2)} \cdot \frac{1.595}{1.56} > \frac{\log \log n}{\log \log N_k}$$

holds for all large enough superabundant numbers $n > m$. □

5 Main Theorem

We use these results:

Proposition 9 [4, Theorem 9 pp. 454]. *The number of superabundant numbers less than x exceeds*

$$\frac{c \cdot \log x \cdot \log \log x}{(\log \log \log x)^2}.$$

Proposition 10 [7, Lemma 1 pp. 2]. *Let $\prod_{j=1}^r p_j^{a_j}$ be the representation of n as a product of primes $p_1 < \dots < p_r$ with natural numbers as exponents a_1, \dots, a_r . Then,*

$$I(n) = \left(\prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 + \frac{1}{p_j} \right) \right) \cdot \left(\prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_j^{a_j+1}} \right) \cdot \frac{p_j^2}{p_j^2 - 1} \right).$$

Proposition 11 [8, pp. 211]. *For all prime numbers $p_k \geq 41$:*

$$R(N_k) \leq 1.56.$$

This is the main theorem.

Theorem 12 *The Riemann hypothesis is true.*

Proof There are infinitely many superabundant numbers by Proposition 9. Let n be a large enough superabundant number such that $7^{100} \mid n$, where p_k is the largest prime factor of n and the k th prime number. Suppose that $\text{Dedekind}(p_k)$ fails. Let $\prod_{i=1}^k p_i^{a_i}$ be the representation of this superabundant number n as the product of the first k consecutive primes $p_1 < \dots < p_k$ with the natural numbers $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k \geq 1$ as exponents, since n must be a Hardy-Ramanujan integer by Proposition 3. First, we show that

$$R(N_k) < \frac{I(n)}{\log \log n}.$$

We know that $\frac{\Psi(n)}{n} = \frac{\Psi(N_k)}{N_k}$ since n must be a Hardy-Ramanujan integer by Proposition 3. It is enough to show that

$$\left(\prod_{i=1}^k \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^{a_i+1}} \right) \cdot \frac{p_i^2}{p_i^2 - 1} \right) > \frac{\log \log n}{\log \log N_k}$$

by Proposition 10. Since n is superabundant and $7^{100} \mid n$, then

$$1.595 > \frac{\log \log n}{\log \log N_k}.$$

by Lemma 4. The inequality

$$1.595 > \frac{\log \log n}{\log \log N_k}$$

holds, because of Lemma 8 and

$$1.595 > \frac{e^\gamma}{\zeta(2)} \cdot \frac{1.595}{1.56}.$$

Therefore, the inequality

$$R(N_k) < \frac{I(n)}{\log \log n}$$

holds under our preconditions as well. That is the same as

$$\frac{\log \log n}{\log \log N_k} \cdot R(N_k) < \frac{I(n)}{\log \log N_k}$$

after of dividing by $\log \log N_k$. That is equivalent to

$$\frac{\log \log n}{\log \log N_k} \cdot 1.56 < \frac{I(n)}{\log \log N_k}$$

by Proposition 11. We use the Lemma 4 and Proposition 10 to show that

$$\frac{\log \log n}{\log \log N_k} \cdot 1.56 < 1.595 \cdot R(N_k)$$

since $\frac{\Psi(n)}{n} = \frac{\Psi(N_k)}{N_k}$. Next, we can see that

$$\frac{\log \log n}{\log \log N_k} \cdot \frac{1.56}{1.595} < \frac{e^\gamma}{\zeta(2)}$$

is equivalent to state that $\text{Dedekind}(p_k)$ holds. We can use the Lemma 8 to check that

$$\frac{\log \log n}{\log \log N_k} < \frac{e^\gamma}{\zeta(2)} \cdot \frac{1.595}{1.56}$$

holds indeed under our preconditions. In this way, we obtain a contradiction under the assumption that $\text{Dedekind}(p_k)$ fails and the existence of such super large superabundant number n . To sum up, the study of this large enough superabundant number n reveals that $\text{Dedekind}(p_k)$ holds on anyway. Accordingly, $\text{Dedekind}(p_{k'})$ holds for all prime numbers $p_{k'}$ such that $p_{k'}$ is the largest prime factor of another superabundant number n' , $n' > n$, $p_{k'} > p_k$ and the k' th prime number. This contradicts the fact that there are infinitely many prime numbers p_k for which $\text{Dedekind}(p_k)$ fails when the Riemann hypothesis is false according to Lemma 2. By reductio ad absurdum, we prove that the Riemann hypothesis is true. \square

6 Conclusions

Practical uses of the Riemann hypothesis include many propositions that are known to be true under the Riemann hypothesis and some that can be shown to be equivalent to the Riemann hypothesis. Indeed, the Riemann hypothesis is closely related to various mathematical topics such as the distribution of primes, the growth of arithmetic functions, the Lindelöf hypothesis, the Large Prime Gap Conjecture, etc. Certainly, a proof of the Riemann hypothesis could spur considerable advances in many mathematical areas, such as number theory and pure mathematics in general.

Acknowledgments. The author wishes to thank Patrick Solé for his helpful comments and Michel Planat for providing the main reference article free of charge. The author also wishes to thank his mother, maternal brother, maternal aunt, and friends Liuva, Yary, Sonia, and Arelis for their support.

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